

Occupational exposure to sharp injuries among medical officers in base hospital in a district of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Health care workers are at risk of exposure to infections like Hepatitis B virus (HBV) Hepatitis C virus (HCV) and human immune-deficiency virus (HIV) due to accidental exposure to contaminated sharp objects. The study was designed to determine the prevalence, correlates, and the post-exposure response of occupational sharp injuries among medical officers in base hospitals in Kalutara District.

A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in all base hospitals in the Kalutara district from April to July 2015. All medical officers and intern house officers with a minimum of six months of working experience were included in the study. A structured, pre-tested self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data and the data was analyzed by using frequency distribution and Chi-square value.

The prevalence of the sharp's injury was 63.4% among the medical officers within their career, about 29.4% of medical officers had been exposed during last year. Medical officers who have 5 years or less experience and who have 5 years or less service experience and who were 30 years or below were more likely to be exposed than others ($p=0.010$ and $p=0.001$ respectively). About 44.2% of medical officers had no satisfactory knowledge. Forty-six percent of medical officers were not satisfied with the arrangement and available space for the workplace. Almost 94% of medical officers were covered with HBV vaccine, however, more than half

vaccinated participants had not been checked for the antibody level. Ten-point seven percent of participants had not developed enough antibody tier. About 81.3% of medical officers had not participated in any training on the matter during their careers.

The majority of exposures had occurred due to suture needles. Operation theatre was the place where a major proportion of exposure had occurred. About 34.5% had just ignored the exposure and 20.8% had done immediate cleaning. Only 38.7% had reported the incidence to take necessary action. Only 5.1% of exposed participants had taken post-exposure prophylaxis during the last 12 months. The study reveals there is considerable risk to percutaneous exposure among medical officers, still, their attention is not adequate regarding the matter.

Keywords: Sharp injuries, Knowledge, Post-exposure prophylaxis, Correlates medical officer

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Introduction

Background

Health care workers (HCW) are the main pillars of the health care system, and their optimal health is essential for the efficient functioning of the system. They work in close contact with infected patients, so at high risk of exposure to blood-borne pathogens due to accidental exposure to blood and body fluid during routine work. The pathogens most commonly transmitted to HCW in the occupational setting are hepatitis B and C viruses and HIV (1). In 2007 the world health organization esteemed global sharps injuries among HCW at two million per year (2). According to past surveys conducted in Sri Lanka on average, 9.5% and 4.3% of health care workers had been exposed to needle stick and cut injuries respectively (3). It was estimated that there were 2.6% of health care workers exposed to the HC virus (HCV), 5.9% of HCW were exposed to the Hepatitis B virus (HBV) and 0.5% were exposed to Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) worldwide annually. Secondary prevention of those infections was expensive and the cost of treating an injury includes treatment of an acquired infection, blood testing, and lost time at work.

Post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) should be initiated, ideally within one hour of the injury, unless the source is known to be negative for HBV, HIV, and HCV. A sharp injury is any cut or pricks from a hypodermic needle, winged steel needle, suture needle, scalpel blade, iv catheter needle, phlebotomy needle, or other sharp objects that any result in percutaneous exposure to blood and body fluids due to previous use on a patient and sustained within the hospital premises.

Justification

World health organization estimated that annually two million needlestick injuries occurred worldwide and 40% to 70% of incidences are underreported (3). Among health care workers (HCW) nurses and physicians appear especially at risk (5). A survey among American surgeons reveals that almost every surgeon experienced at least one such injury during their training (6). In Sri Lanka, there is no national surveillance program to collect data regarding occupational sharps injuries among health care workers to occupational sharp injury in Sri Lanka (7).

Objectives

To determine the prevalence correlates and the post-exposure response of occupational sharp injuries among medical officers in base hospitals in Kalutara district.

Methodology

The descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Base hospitals in Kalutara district from 01st of April to 31st of July 2015. The target study population of this survey was all medical officers attached to the four selected hospitals in Kalutara District. The medical officers who have been working in the 4 base hospitals for more than 6 months were included in the study (287). The data was collected by using a structured self-administered questionnaire from the study participants. The questionnaire was pre-tested in base hospital Homagama. A self-administered questionnaire was used to assess the prevalence, correlates, and post-exposure response of sharps injuries among medical officers in the research setting. The principal investigator and trained assistant collected data. The questions were coded by using a codebook for the convenience of data entry. The analysis of data was done by the principal investigator using the

statistical package for social science (SPSS) software by using a personal computer. Appropriate frequency distribution and cross-tabulation were done to match the specific objectives. The Chi-square test was used wherever appropriate to assess their association. A P-value less than 0.05 was used to determine the significance.

Results

The study includes 265 participants with a response rate of 92.3% (265).

Knowledge of sharps injuries.

Table 01: distribution of study population by overall knowledge and knowledge on post exposure management of sharp injuries.

Parameter	Number	percentage
Overall knowledge on sharps injuries		
satisfactory	148	55.8%
Not satisfactory	117	44.2%
Knowledge on post exposure management		
Good	161	60.8%
Poor	104	39.2%

Of the study population, 55.8% were categorized as having a satisfactory overall knowledge of sharps injury. Among the study population, 60.8% had shown a good level of knowledge on post-exposure-response.

Twenty-four-point five percent of study participants never practiced recapping and 53.2% declared they do recap on some occasions. 24.5% declared they always do recap as a habit. Among the study population, 58.1% declared that they use

gloves always involving sharps whereas 41.9 declared there were some occasions of not using gloves when handling sharps.

Immunization status for HBV

Antibody titre following vaccination

Checked	112	43.4%	258
Not checked	146	56.5%	100%

Enough antibody coverage.

Developed	100	89.3%	112
Not developed	12	10.7%	100%

Immunization status for HBV

Table 2: Distribution of immunization status of the study population for Hepatitis B

Immunization status	Number.	Total
	%	
Immunization against HBV		
Done.	258	265
Not done	7	
	97.4%	100%
	2.6%	

Ninety-seven-point four percent had taken at least 1 dose of hepatitis B vaccine and only 7(2.6%) medical officers had not taken the vaccine at all. Only 49(18.7%) participated in at least one training while 213(81.3%) medical officers had not attended any training on occupational safety.

Exposure to a sharp injury

Table 3: Distribution of exposure status to sharps injury among study population

Exposure status	Number %	Total Number %
Ever exposed	168	265 100%
Not exposed	97	
	63.4%	
	36.6%	
Exposed within last 12 month	78	265 100%
Yes	29.4%	
No	187	
	70.6%	
Frequency of exposure within last 12 months		
1 time exposure	33	78 100%
>1 exposure	45	
	42.3 %	
	57.7 %	

It was stated that 63.4% of medical officers in the study population had been exposed to occupational sharps injury sometimes during their career.

Table 4: Distribution of medical officers by exposure to occupational sharps injury during the last 12 months and selected background characteristics

Background characteristics	Not exposed (within last 12 months) No. percentage	Exposed (within last 12 months) No. percentage	significance
Experience			
Below 5 years	71 62.3%	43 37.7%	X ² =6.512 df=1 p= 0.010
Above 5 years	116 76.8%	35 23.2%	
Age			
30 & below 30 years	40 54.8%	33 45.2%	X ² =12.066 df=1 P=0.001
Above 30 years	147 76.6%	45 23.4%	
Sex			
Male	73 64.6%	40 35.4%	X ² =3.374 df=1 p=0.066
Female	114 75.0%	38 25%	

The proportion of participants who were exposed to sharps injury within the last 12 months was significantly higher among the group with service experience of 5 years or less, compared to the group with service experience of more than 5 years. (p=0.010) Medical officers who were 30 years or below showed a significantly higher proportion of exposure (p=0.001) to sharps injury compared to the group above 30 years.

The suture needle was the most frequently reported instrument. According to the study, the highest frequency of exposure had occurred in operation theatres (38.1%) and then inward settings (16.7%) Suturing was the procedure accountable for the majority of exposures (38.1%). Own

careless practice was mentioned as an immediate perceived cause for exposure by the majority of participants (44%).

Post exposure-response

It was found that 7.7% of exposed participants had ignored the incident totally without taking any preventive measure and 45% of exposed participants had taken brief history to assess the risk from the source person and ignored it. About 20.8% of participants had done some immediate cleaning with soap or disinfectant with or without squeezing the lesion to promote bleeding. Only 38.7% of the exposed participants had reported to the relevant authority.

Table 5: Distribution of medical officers by period of exposure, reporting and taking prophylaxis for the percutaneous exposure of Blood and Body Fluids (BBF)

Parameter Number	Number		Total
		Percentage	Percentage
Exposed			
before the past year	90	53.6%	168
within the past year	78	46.4%	
Within the past year	32	41%	100%
Reporting done	46	59%	78
Reporting not done			100%
PEP following exposure within the year	04	5.1%	78
Taken		94.9%	100%
Not taken			

Of those exposed, 46.4% had been exposed within the past year and of them, only 41% had reported to the relevant department for further investigation. It was found that the majority of not reporting participants (49.5%) assumed the incident as not harmful and ignored it.

Discussion

Of the 265 participants, 78 had been exposed within the past year, giving a prevalence of 29.4% due to occupational exposure to blood and body fluid from sharps injuries among medical officers. Of those sharps injuries, 85.9% were attributable to needle stick injuries and 14.1% were attributable to cut injuries. An almost similar result was reported in another study by Karawita D.A. (3). Out of the above, 29.4% in the present study, 57.7% had been exposed to more than once during the year and 63.4% of participants had been exposed at least once in their career.

This finding is supported by other international studies which show 54% exposure to needle stick injury among trainee doctors in a university hospital in the UK during their career (8). The difference may be due to the fact that they have considered only needle stick injuries instead of all percutaneous injuries.

The study revealed that the medical officers who had a service experience of 5 years or less are more likely to be exposed than those who had a service experience of over 5 years ($p=0.010$). Also, the participants who were 30 years or below has a significantly high chance of exposure than who were above 30 years ($p=0.001$). Junior medical officers work long hours than senior officers and their lack of experience can be considered as the reason for this. However, this is different from the findings of Ibtissam (9).

Considering the overall knowledge on percutaneous exposure, it was satisfactory among 55.8% of participants. Quite similar findings were explained by Karawita (3).

Sixty Point eight percent of participants have had good knowledge of post-exposure management. Similar results were obtained

by Ibtissam (10). In the present study, the exposed group had more knowledge than the non-exposed group ($p=0.036$).

The study shows, 77.7% of participants practice recapping during their career. Almost similar results were obtained by Wilson (10). However, these figures are much higher compared to the developed countries like the United Kingdom where recapping was reported as 43% among physicians (11).

Immunization coverage for hepatitis B among participants was 98%. Similar results were obtained by Raghvendran (11) in the United Kingdom. However, checking for antibody levels following vaccination was not satisfactory. It was recommended to check antibody level at 6 weeks or later following the full course of HBV vaccination (12). Among the participants who checked the antibody level following the full course of vaccination, 10.7% did not have enough antibody coverage for Hepatitis B.

Fifty-four-point two percent of participants were exposed while doing a procedure on their own. A different finding was reported by another study showing 40% of injured personnel not being the original user (13). In their survey, several categories of health care workers were included, which may explain the difference in the results.

Suture needle was identified as the commonest causative device contributing to 38.2% of causes. The above findings are different from data presented by CDC which shows the majority of exposure was due to hollow bore needle and followed by glass and thirdly by suture needle (14). That difference may be due to the fact that CDC had considered percutaneous exposures among all health care workers unlike in the present study.

Suturing was the major activity contributing to 38.1% of the exposures among medical officers. The finding suggests the use of safety devices such as blunt-tip suture needles wherever clinically appropriate rather than sharp tip suture needles (15).

Considering the place of occurrence, operation theatre was identified as the place where the majority of incidents happened (38.1%). These findings are quite different from other studies where most of them identified the ward as the place where the majority of them identified the ward as the place where the majority of incidents happened and operation theatre as second and third place (16). In the present study, only 41% of the exposed participants reported the incident to the relevant authority for follow-up, during the past year. Similar results were obtained by Markovic (17) of Serbia.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study recommends having continuous awareness programs and training on this subject and also updating the content of the training curricula. Still, there is a minor proportion of medical officers without obtaining the vaccine for Hepatitis B. Hence, facilities should be provided to obtain 100% immunization coverage for HBV, provide facilities to obtain booster doses and attach non-respondents to low-risk units. Always keep available post-exposure prophylaxis in the institutions and make the staff aware of its availability. Furthermore, the provision of safety devices by the management should be encouraged as much as possible

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